

LETTERS

Pauling points to "errors" in the review of his book

□ The review of my book "How to Live Longer and Feel Better" (W.H. Freeman & Company, New York, 1986) by Professor F.M. Clydesdale of the University of Massachusetts, Amherst (*Food Technology*, p. 152, March 1987) contains a serious error in two of its six paragraphs.

In the second paragraph the reviewer states that I promote the use of 20,000 to 40,000 milligrams of vitamin C per day, and dismiss any disagreements by referring to them as the "old nutrition." The discussion of 20,000 to 40,000 mg of vitamin C per day is continued in the third paragraph.

In fact, in the table on page 11 of my book my recommendation is given as 1,000 to 18,000 mg per day. Two lines below are the numbers 20,000 to 40,000, referring to another vitamin. I suggest that the reviewer glanced at the table, and thought that 20,000 to 40,000 referred to vitamin C. Much of his criticism of my book is based on this error that he made. In the text of my book (page 78) I state that the amount of individual biochemical variability is such that for a large population the optimum daily intake of vitamin C may vary between 250 mg and 20,000 mg per day, and that my conclusion is that for most of adult human beings it lies in the range 2,300 mg to 10,000 mg. My associate Dr. Ewan Cameron has treated several hundred patients with advanced cancer by giving them 10,000 mg of vitamin C per day, and in my book I mention some cancer patients who have been taking 36,000 mg per day.

The reviewer also asks if it might be permissible to inquire about the "old nutritional" proof of the toxicity of vitamins A and D. In fact, this old evidence is discussed in some detail on pages 254 to 255.

—Linus Pauling, Linus Pauling Institute of Science and Medicine, Palo Alto, Calif. 94306

□ In response to Dr. Pauling's letter I would like to point out that the serious errors he describes are not in fact errors. It is true that on page 11 of his book the recommendations for Vitamin C is 1,000 to 18,000 mg per day, however I reviewed the entire book and not just the Table on this page. The recommendation for 40,000 mg of Vitamin C per day may be found in the last three lines on page 111, "The amount of protection increases with increase in the amount of ingested Vitamin C and becomes nearly complete with 10g to 40g per day taken at the immediate onset of the cold."

In answer to the second comment concerning the toxicity of Vitamins A and D I feel that the four paragraphs spread over pages 252 and 253 (not 254 and 255 stated in Dr. Pauling's letter) which tend to belittle the dangers of overdose are just not enough in a book of 322 pages recommending megadoses of vitamins and intended for a lay audience. In fact the sentence on page 251 which states "Nobody dies of poisoning by an overdose of vitamins" lessens the dangers far too much for the readership of this book.

—F.M. Clydesdale, Professor, Dept. of Food Science and Nutrition, U of Massachusetts at Amherst

Toxicology of "antioxidant" spices is indeed unknown

□ In the article, "Future Trends for Flavorings and Spices," by Sally K. Williams and W.L. Brown, (*Food Technology*, p. 76, June 1987) the comment was made that "the demand for flavorings with natural antioxidant properties will begin to escalate as consumers become more health oriented, and as

scientists continue to study carcinogenic effects of chemical ingredients used as antioxidants."

While not arguing with the first half of that statement, the comment on carcinogenic effects requires deeper consideration. All antioxidants have physiological effects and the natural antioxidants display similar adverse effects to the synthetics at high doses. The protective, i.e., anticancer, effects of antioxidants—including the synthetics, is well documented and the particular activity of the synthetics, such as BHA, against aflatoxin, is highly significant in the "healthy eating trend." The toxicology of spice extracts is, as yet, virtually unknown territory.

There are already indications of a demand from those who consider themselves ahead of the game for the more potent synthetic antioxidants because of their perceived anticancer, antiaging properties.

—P.P. Coppen, International Marketing Manager, Industrial Chemicals, May & Baker Ltd., Dagenham Essex, England

□ The authors agree—the toxicology of spice extracts is virtually unknown.

IFT's Classified Guide, an invaluable resource

□ We are interested in obtaining the latest IFT Classified Guide to Food Industry Services. It has proven to be an invaluable resource that students have used in our Career Library.

—Jose Magdalene, Career Counselor, Montclair State College, Upper Montclair, NJ

□ This is just one of the many, many requests we have received for our Classified Guide. Almost all requests, however, have come from food technologists in industry who are looking for consultants or contract services. We are happy to hear that students also find this publication of value.

Reprints of the 1987 Classified Guide are still available (see advertisement on p. 177 of the October issue).

IFT's 1988 Classified Guide to Food Industry Services will be published in December 1987 issue of *Food Technology*.

EDUCATION NEWS

(Continued from page 24)

how certain components of wheat flour affect the end-use properties of doughs. The research will be conducted by Constant Addo, a doctoral candidate, originally from Ghana, who will use some of the French company's testing equipment in the project.

The specific purpose of the research will be to look at how compositional factors govern physical, physicochemical and rheological properties of doughs. When the significance of specific components of wheat has been established as important, tests can then be developed to detect them and screen them out or increase their amount by classical or novel breeding programs.

Pomeranz joined the faculty of Washington State University ten months ago to work on international marketing problems for the International Marketing Program for Agricultural Commodities and Trade (IMPACT). During this short span of time, Pomeranz has received a series of grants and gifts, totaling \$240,000 (including the French company gift), in support of his research projects on grains and cereals.